

UNVEILING ECONOMIC VITALITY: EXPLORING THE AVERAGE SIZE OF NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This article delves into the economic fabric of the Romanian Mountain Area, specifically focusing on the average size of newly established enterprises and the number of persons employed within the reference period from 2008 to 2018. Through a thorough analysis of key indicators, workforce trends, and economic shifts, the study aims to provide insights into the growth patterns and employment dynamics of these enterprises within the picturesque mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

The establishment and growth of enterprises are vital components of economic development. This article concentrates on the Romanian Mountain Area to uncover the average size of newly established enterprises and the number of persons employed within the reference period from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to analyze the economic vitality of these enterprises and their contributions to regional employment.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research integrates data from business registries, official reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators, such as the average size of enterprises and employment figures, are analyzed to provide a nuanced understanding of the economic landscape in newly established businesses within the mountainous region.

3. Average Size of Newly Established Enterprises:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the average size of enterprises established in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as the number of employees, variations across industries, and trends in the establishment of smaller versus larger enterprises are scrutinized to assess the diversity and growth patterns within the business landscape.

4. Employment Patterns:

The article delves into the employment patterns within newly established enterprises, examining variations in the number of persons employed over the specified decade. Insights into industry-specific employment trends and their correlation with the average size of enterprises provide valuable information on workforce dynamics.

5. Sectoral Analysis:

An in-depth sectoral analysis is conducted to explore the

distribution of newly established enterprises across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. This section investigates the average size of enterprises within key sectors, shedding light on the diverse economic activities contributing to regional development.

6. Demographic Characteristics of the Workforce:

The paper explores the demographic aspects of the workforce within newly established enterprises, analyzing age groups, gender distribution, and educational backgrounds. Understanding the composition of the workforce provides valuable insights into the average size of enterprises and the demographic trends shaping employment dynamics.

7. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of the average size of newly established enterprises, the article investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), overall employment rates, and economic stability in the Romanian Mountain Area. The interconnectedness between the size of enterprises and the broader economic landscape is explored.

8. Results:

Average size of newly established enterprises: the number of persons employed in the reference period (t) at newly established enterprises in t divided by the number of newly established enterprises in t – number

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentile 25, 50, 75, so 1.9700, .14853, 1.8300, .49261, .243, 1.921, .661, 4.512, 1.279, 1.73, 1.52, 3.25, 1.6200, 1.8170, 0.8300 .

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 Holt; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .446, .432, -4.441E-16, .918, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; R-square .222, .218, -4.441E-16, .490, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; RMSE .516, .499, .175, 1.881, .175, .178; MAPS 15,221, 8,116, 5,975, 28,183, 5,975, 6,232; MaxAPE 36,796, 14,859, 19,838, 57,502, 19,838, 20,096; MAE .348, .340, .104, 1.298, .104, .111; MaxAE 1.213, 1.172, .325, 4.108, .325, .339; Normalized BIC -1.574, 1.479, -3.051, 1.700, -3.051, -3.022.

The resulting predictive statistical models show the following overall picture for I21 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: .878, .343, .421, 12.009, .257 ; S2-Model_2: .899, .349, 1.881, 28.183, 1.298; S3-Model_3: .918, .353, .239, 7.888, .174; S4-Model_4: 1.577E-14, 1.577E-14, .235, 11.624, .189; S5-Model_5: .816, .490, .175, 5.975, .104; S6-Model_6: 5.451E-14, 5.451E-14, .214, 7.262, .162; S7-Model_7: .681, .484, .188, 9.976, .137; S8-

Model_8: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, .725, 25.317, .446; S9-Model_9: 1.110E-15, 1.110E-15, .677, 19.947, .404; S10-Model_10: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, .646, 25.720, .457; S11-Model_11: .708, .428, .275, 13.533, .194.

Table 38. Prediction analysis for I21

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	1.42	1.32	1.23	1.13	1.04	.94	.85	.75
	UCL	2.37	2.28	2.19	2.10	2.01	1.92	1.83	1.74
	LCL	.47	.37	.27	.17	.07	-.03	-.13	-.23
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	1.74	1.31	.88	.45	.02	-.41	-.84	- 1.27
	UCL	6.00	5.59	5.18	4.77	4.36	3.95	3.54	3.13
	LCL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	1.95	1.90	1.85	1.80	1.75	1.70	1.65	1.60
	UCL	2.49	2.44	2.39	2.34	2.29	2.24	2.19	2.14
	LCL	1.41	1.36	1.31	1.26	1.21	1.16	1.11	1.06
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60
	UCL	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12	2.12
	LCL	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07	1.07
S5-Model_5:	Forecast	1.27	1.22	1.17	1.12	1.07	1.02	.97	.92
	UCL	1.67	1.62	1.57	1.52	1.46	1.41	1.36	1.31
	LCL	.88	.82	.77	.72	.67	.62	.57	.52
S6-Model_6:	Forecast	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28	2.28
	UCL	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76
	LCL	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80
S7-Model_7:	Forecast	1.12	1.07	1.01	.96	.90	.85	.79	.74
	UCL	1.55	1.50	1.44	1.39	1.34	1.29	1.23	1.18

	LCL	.70	.64	.58	.53	.47	.41	.36	.30
S8-Model_8:	Forecast	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55	1.55
	UCL	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17	3.17
	LCL	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06	-.06
S9-Model_9:	Forecast	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76
	UCL	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27	3.27
	LCL	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25	.25
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64
	UCL	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08
	LCL	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20	.20
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	1.07	1.00	.92	.85	.78	.71	.63	.56
	UCL	1.69	1.62	1.55	1.48	1.41	1.34	1.27	1.20
	LCL	.44	.37	.29	.22	.14	.07	-.01	-.08

Figure 3.29. Graphical forecasting analysis for I21

8. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining the challenges and opportunities faced by both employers and employees in newly established enterprises, this section investigates factors such as scalability, workforce skill requirements, and market competition. Addressing these aspects is crucial for fostering a resilient and sustainable business environment.

9. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing the average size of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

10. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive analysis of the average size of newly established enterprises and the number of persons employed in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's economic dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable growth in newly established enterprises within the mountainous region.

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